

STUDY OF ALLERGIZING ACTIVITY OF THE DRUG «NETINFLA №2»

M.S.Khikmatova

Tashkent pharmaceutical institute, Tashkent, Republic of Uzbekistan

e-mail: mutabarkhon.jurabekk@gmail.com phone: +998970112274

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Abstract: Successful introduction of new medicines into clinical practice presupposes the proven safety of their use. For this purpose, it is important to conduct preclinical pilot studies. Scientific methods are used to assess and prove the safety of drugs, as a requisite for the use of new drugs created for the first time in humans is previous conduct of toxicological studies on laboratory animals. One of the necessary toxicological studies is the study of allergizing activity

Purpose: Study of allergizing activity of the drug « Netinfla №2»

Methods: Allergizing effect of the drug was studied by conjunctival test. White mice (both sexes) weighing 20-22g, 10 animals in total, were used in the experiment. Therefore, the animals were injected subcutaneously once with 5% solution of hen's egg albumin (prepared on physiological solution) in the volume of 1ml/20g. On the 10th day a conjunctival test was performed. Hence, 1 drop of the drug, under the lower eyelid of the right eye was placed under the lower eyelid of the right eye using pipette with an extended end, under the conventional name "Netinfla" at a dose of 6000 mg/kg, and 1 drop of physiological solution (control) was placed under the lower eyelid of the left eye. The reaction was recorded after 15 minutes (fast reaction) and after 24-48 hours (delayed-type hypersensitive) and evaluated on the following scale (in points): 0 - no reaction; 1 - slight reddening of the lacrimal duct; 2- reddening of the lacrimal ducts and sclera towards the cornea; 3 - reddening of the whole conjunctiva and sclera, reaction accompanied by itching and when brushing with the paws it is possible to develop purulent ophthalmitis. The revealed differences in the condition of the test and control of the eyes were described

Results: In result, 10 days after the conjunctival test with "Netinfla №2", the results were as follows, shown in the table 6.

Table 6

Results of allergen activity of the drug "Netinfla".

Designation of experimental animals	15 minutes after installation	24 hours after installation	48 hours after installation
Experimental group №1			
0			
Experimental group №2			
0			

As indicated in the Table 6, both rapid reactions (15 minutes) and delayed- type hypersensitivity (24-48 hours) were absent in sentinel experimental animals. There were no differences between the state of the left and right eyes in any animal: the conjunctiva was pale

pink in color, redness of the lacrimal duct and sclera was not observed, and there was no discharge from the eyes.

Conclusion: Allergic activity of the pharmacological agent “Netinfla №2” was studied, the obtained data indicates the absence of allergic effect of the remedy “Netinfla №2”.